

THE EFFECT OF EXPORT CLOUD MARKET PLATFORM BASED ON LOCAL POTENTIAL ON BUSINESS PERFORMANCE, TECHNOLOGY ADOPTION, MARKETING ORIENTATION WITH INNOVATIVE TRAINING VARIABLE MODERATION

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Abstract

Indonesia's export sector has undergone a significant evolution, as reflected in the growth that continues to increase yearly. This increase was driven by the performance of MSMEs, the backbone of the Indonesian economy, because of their large number and even distribution throughout the country. However, there are gaps in technology adoption and implementation of practices at the operational level for MSMEs. This is exacerbated by a low understanding of what motivates MSME owners to develop structured and effective business plans. This study aims to investigate the impact of local potential-based export cloud market platforms on business performance, technology adoption, and MSME marketing orientation by considering the role of innovative training as a moderation variable. Data was obtained from a survey of 100 MSMEs in Indonesia. The analysis results show that the export cloud market platform based on local potential significantly influences business performance, technology adoption, and MSME marketing orientation. In addition, innovative training was also found to mediate the relationship between the platform and these variables. The practical implication of this research is the need to develop innovative training programs focused on supporting MSMEs in utilizing technology platforms effectively to improve business performance

and adaptation to digital market trends. This research enriches understanding of how MSMEs can utilize the export cloud market platform for business growth and sustainability.

Index Terms: Export Platform, Business Performance, Technology Adoption, Marketing Orientation, Innovative Training.

1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia has a strategic position as an archipelagic country, which gives it great economic potential, especially in the export sector [1]. This unique geographical condition gives Indonesia a great competitive advantage in the export sector, and its great economic potential can be seen from various aspects [2]. Changes in global trade dynamics in Indonesia's export sector have undergone a significant evolution [3].

Exports in Indonesia have continued to experience positive growth in recent decades, with Indonesia's export value in 2020 [4]. Therefore, developing export power in Indonesia is an urgent imperative given the country's strategic position in the global economic map, especially for the small business sector [5]. Small businesses can be a key driver of growth, job creation, and source of innovation [6].

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are very important in supporting export growth in Indonesia [7]. MSMEs are the backbone of the Indonesian economy because of their large number and are evenly distributed throughout the country [8]. MSMEs generally employ most of a country's workforce, so increasing export activities from this sector will directly impact increasing people's income and welfare [9]. The development of MSME export strength is also important to diversify a country's economic base [10]. A diverse export sector within a country will be better able to cope with global market volatility and unexpected economic changes [11].

MSMEs have a comparative advantage in producing certain goods and services by expanding market reach through exports [12]. Therefore, the progress of MSMEs is strongly influenced by the existence and commitment of business owners to becoming a determining factor in the success and sustainability of business in the future [13].

MSME owners have a central role in determining the direction and success of MSME businesses [14]. Business owners are responsible for strategic decision-making, planning, and implementation of business initiatives [15]. This central role is important because MSME owners directly influence the business, from product or service development to financial and human resource management [16].

MSME owners have a major role in setting the vision, mission, and business goals, so they are responsible for formulating the right business strategy according to market conditions and customer needs [17]. The decisions taken by MSME owners, in this case, will greatly affect the direction and continuity of the MSME business [18]. Concrete steps can be taken to improve the quality of MSMEs through improvements in the strategic, technical, and technology adoption in the form of training for MSME owners in developing effective business plans [19].

However, challenges such as changes in global trade dynamics and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic demand adaptation and new strategies to increase Indonesia's export competitiveness in the international market [20]. The Indonesian government has taken strategic steps to address these challenges [21]. One is boosting export market diversification, especially for creative, non-oil, and gas products (Karanfil & Omgba, 2023). In addition, the government also provides stimulus and incentives to business actors to strengthen export competitiveness [23].

The government's preventive measures include providing business capital assistance, export tax exemption, and faster and easier export license management facilities [24]. However, there are gaps in technology adoption and the application of practices at the operational level for MSMEs, which are important pillars of export support [25]. This is exacerbated by a low understanding of what motivates MSME owners to develop structured and effective business plans [18].

Therefore, this study focuses on assessing the influence of the local potential-based export cloud market platform on empowering local MSME exports. This study examines the influence on business performance, technology adoption, and marketing orientation with innovative training on moderation variables. This research has several formulations of problems: first, how does the local potential-based export cloud market platform affect the business performance of MSMEs? Second, how does the local potential-based export cloud market platform impact technology adoption? Third, what is the contribution of the local potential-based export cloud market platform in fostering a new marketing orientation for MSMEs? Finally, how does innovative training moderate the relationship between export cloud market platforms based on local potential, business performance, technology adoption, and marketing orientation? These questions detail the key elements you want to uncover and explore during the research process.

The implications of this research are very significant because it can provide a clearer view of how the use of export cloud market platforms based on local potential can affect business performance, technology adoption, and marketing orientation of a local MSME. MSMEs can take strategic steps to improve operational efficiency, optimize technology utilization, and develop more effective marketing strategies based on reviews that have been implemented [26].

Innovative training as a moderation variable also allows companies to improve employee capabilities and knowledge in facing technological changes and market dynamics [27]. In addition, this research has far-reaching implications for local MSMEs directly involved in exports and the overall business ecosystem [28].

On a macro scale, this research can also assist the government and related institutions in formulating more effective policies and programs to support export business development, strengthen national economic competitiveness, and improve community welfare by increasing employment and income [29]. This research can potentially be the foundation for developing better business strategies and economic policies in the future [30].

2. BACKGROUND OF THEORIES AND HYPOTHESES

2.1 Digital Transformation through Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential

The rapid development of information and communication technology has given MSMEs wider access to the global market through digital platforms. The export cloud market platform allows MSMEs to develop MSME businesses more effectively and efficiently, especially in promoting MSME products or services to international markets. Use features like inventory management system integration, easy payment processing, and in-depth market analysis [31]. MSMEs can take advantage of the local potential of MSMEs to create products that attract global market interest. The export cloud market platform also allows MSMEs to interact directly with buyers from various countries, reducing communication and transaction barriers that are often obstacles in traditional export businesses [32]. One of the main advantages of digital transformation through the export cloud market platform is its ability to improve the operational efficiency of MSMEs. With an adequate automation and integration system, MSMEs can better manage MSME inventory, process orders quickly and accurately, and monitor MSME business performance in real time [33]. Digital export platforms have a higher operational efficiency, with shorter processing times and lower administrative costs compared to conventional methods. In addition, digital transformation also allows MSMEs to utilize market data and analysis more effectively in developing MSME marketing strategies [34].

However, to take full advantage of this digital transformation potential, MSMEs need to have adequate skills and knowledge in the use of technology [35]. Digital transformation through the Export Cloud Market Platform based on local potential has great potential to increase the competitiveness of MSMEs in the global market, drive economic growth, and encourage overall community development. Based on the presentation of existing problems, the research hypothesis is described as follows:

- H1. The Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential has a significant positive impact on Business Performance.
- H2. The Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential has a significant positive impact on Technology Adoption.
- H3. The Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential has a significant positive impact on Marketing Orientation.

2.2 Innovative Training Strategy in Improving the Competitiveness of Local MSMEs

Innovative training strategies are key in improving local MSMEs' competitiveness amid changing market dynamics. The business ecosystem is increasingly complex and affected by technological advances, so MSMEs must strengthen their capabilities to compete effectively [36]. MSMEs often face challenges in keeping up with technological developments and optimizing them to develop MSME businesses. Therefore, innovative training strategies have become important [37]. One important aspect of innovative training strategies is the improvement of skills in the use of digital technology. In this

digital era, leveraging technology is key to improving operational efficiency, reaching a wider market, and expanding business reach [28]. Skills such as leadership, creativity, teamwork, and adaptability to changing business environments become highly relevant in the face of complex challenges. This training program that includes the development of soft skills can help MSMEs build strong teams, increase productivity, and respond to market changes more flexibly [38].

Innovative training strategies have great potential to increase the competitiveness of local MSMEs, strengthen the contribution of MSMEs to the national economy, and improve the overall welfare of society [39]. Therefore, governments, educational institutions, and other stakeholders must collaborate to develop and implement effective and sustainable innovative training programs. Thus, MSMEs will be better prepared to face future challenges and take advantage of existing opportunities for sustainable business growth. Based on the explanation discussed, the following assumptions are made.

H4. Innovative Training has a significant positive impact on Business Performance.

H5. Innovative Training has a significant positive impact on Technology Adoption.

H6. Innovative Training has a significant positive impact on Marketing Orientation.

H7. Innovative Training plays an intermediary role in the Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential for Business Performance, Technology Adoption, and Marketing Orientation.

Based on the formulation of the seven hypotheses above, the formulation of the conceptual framework of the research is as follows:

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

3. METHODOLOGISTS

3.1 Research Design

The research methodology used in this study is quantitative with an empirical normative approach. The study was conducted using the Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method with Smart PLS software to prove the validity of the hypothesis proposed. An empirical normative approach was chosen to examine the relationship between the variables tested with a strong theoretical foundation and supported by empirical data collected through questionnaires. The data source for this study was obtained from respondents who filled out questionnaires using a five-point Likert scale [40].

3.2 Research Design

This research was conducted in Malang Regency, East Java, as a research location chosen carefully. Malang Regency was chosen because it has characteristics that represent the context of MSMEs in Indonesia in general. In contrast, East Java significantly contributes to the national economy through the MSME sector. Thus, this research is expected to show how MSMEs in Indonesia, especially in Malang Regency, can develop MSME businesses through the Export Cloud Market Platform. This research involved 100 respondents of MSME actors in Malang Regency.

Table 1: Research Variables And Dimensions

Variable	Dimension	Measurement	Previous Research or Questionnaires
Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential (X1)	Platform Accessibility	Access Speed	[31], [34], [41], [42]
		Connection Availability	
		Connection Stability	
		Device Compatibility	
	Business Continuity	Resource Usage	
		Community Engagement	
		Social Engagement	
		Sustainable Business Model	
	Operational Efficiency	Use of Technology	
		Process Automation	
Data Management			
Improved Service Quality			
Business Performance (Y1)	Market Share	Pangsa Pasar	[43]–[46]
		Growth of Market Flats	
		Competitive Advantage	
		Product Diversification	
	Product or Service Quality	Customer Satisfaction	
		Product Reliability	
		Product Innovation	
		Suitability to Needs	
	Sales Growth	Revenue Growth	
		Changes in Sales Volume	
Achievement of Sales Targets			

		Market Penetration	
Technology Adoption (Y2)	Technology Skills	Technology Understanding	[31], [47]–[50]
		Usage Expertise	
		Technology Creativity	
		Technology Troubleshooting Capabilities	
	Trust in Technology	Technology Reliability	
		Information Security	
		Ease of Use	
		Belief in Benefits	
	Technology Performance Measurement	Operational Efficiency	
		Work Productivity	
Quality of Results			
System Responsiveness			
Marketing Orientation (Y3)	Market Orientation	Understanding Customer Needs	[47], [51]–[53]
		Customer Responsiveness	
		Focus on Quality of Service	
		Customer-Driven Innovation	
	Marketing Innovation	The Desire to Innovate	
		Application of Creative Ideas	
		A Sense of Innovation Urgency	
		Marketing Innovation Performance Evaluation	
	Market Segmentation	Market Segment Identification	
		Product or Service Differentiation	
Specialized Communication			
Meeting Unique Needs			
Innovative Training (Z1)	Participation in Training	Willingness to Participate	[1], [37], [39], [54]
		Activities in Discussion	
		Involvement in Practical Exercises	
		Enthusiasm for training materials	
	Training Methods	Availability of Learning Resource Materials	
		Use of Innovative Technology	
		Interactive Approach	
		Case-Based Learning Method	
	Training Content	Relevance of Training Materials	
		Linkage to Individual Needs	

The data analysis methodology is carried out inductively, where the data collected from questionnaires distributed to respondents in Malang Regency are analyzed to find patterns or relationships that may exist among the variables studied without having previous assumptions. Data collected through a 5-point Likert scale will be analyzed using Smart PLS software to prove the validity of the proposed hypothesis. The statistical analysis will help understand how much influence the Export Cloud Market Platform has on business performance, technology adoption, and marketing orientation of MSMEs, as well as the extent to which innovative training moderates the relationship between these variables.

3.3 Data Analysis

To test the models and hypotheses proposed in this study, we used the partial least squares (PLS) method, a structural equation modeling (SEM) technique that has proven effective in quantitative data analysis. PLS is a major component-based estimation approach used to examine the relationship between variables in the proposed model. In the context of our research, PLS is used to analyze the relationship between local potential-based export cloud market platforms and other dependent variables, namely business performance, technology adoption, and marketing orientation, and moderate the effect of innovative training on these relationships [55].

The first step in using PLS is evaluating the outer model, including convergent validity, construct validity, discriminant validity, and reliability comparison. Convergent validity evaluation ensures that each variable indicator has a significant and consistent load factor. Construct validity is evaluated by examining each construct's loading factor and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). In contrast, discriminant validity ensures that each construct is distinguishable. Construct reliability is measured using Cronbach's alpha and Composite Reliability (CR) values, and reliability comparisons are carried out to assess consistency between indicators [56].

After the outer model evaluation is complete, the analysis continues on the inner model. Evaluation of the inner model involves assessing the coefficient of determination (R-squared), predictive relevance (Q-squared), goodness of fit, and inner weight. The coefficient of determination measures how well the model can account for variations in the dependent variable. Predictive relevance (Q-squared) measures the model's ability to predict the value of an unobserved dependent variable. The goodness of fit is used to evaluate how well the model fits the observed data, while inner weight measures the strength of inter-variable relationships in the model [57].

This evaluation step can determine the extent to which the proposed model follows the observed data and whether the proposed hypothesis can be accepted or rejected based on the analysis results. The results of this evaluation will provide deep insight into the inter-variable relationships in the context of our research and provide a solid basis for making conclusions and implications of our research findings. Thus, using PLS methods in our data analysis is expected to better understand MSME business dynamics in facing challenges and opportunities in today's digital era [58]

4. METHODOLOGISTS

4.1 Uji Outer Model

The outer model includes an assessment of the indicators or variables used in constructing the model. The first step in this evaluation is to check convergent validity. Convergent validity is used to ensure that each indicator has a significant contribution to measuring the construct in question. This is indicated by the high and significant level of loading factor in each indicator. Next, construct validity is examined, including evaluating AVE (Average Variance Extracted) and loading factors. The AVE must exceed a value of

0.5 to indicate that the construct has sufficient variance to be considered valid [55]. In addition, discriminant validity is also checked to ensure that each construct is distinguishable. This is done by comparing the AVE value with the squared correlations between the constructs. In addition, construct reliability is also checked using Cronbach's alpha and Composite Reliability (CR) values [56]. The outer model evaluation also includes reliability comparisons between indicators to ensure consistency between indicators used in the construct.

4.1.1 Convergent Validity

The Convergent Validity test is used to ensure that each variable indicator significantly contributes to measuring the construct in question. This is done by checking each indicator's high and significant loading factor level. If the loading factor of these indicators is high and significant, then it can be considered that the indicators converge well with the measured construct. In other words, the Convergent Validity test helps ensure that variable indicators consistently represent the same construct in the research model [57].

Table 2: Loading Factor

Variable	Dimension	Item	Loading Value	Information
Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential (X1)	Platform Accessibility	X11	0.952	VALID
	Business Continuity	X12	0.965	VALID
	Operational Efficiency	X13	0.959	VALID
Business Performance (Y1)	Market Share	Y11	0.935	VALID
	Product or Service Quality	Y12	0.925	VALID
	Sales Growth	Y13	0.905	VALID
Technology Adoption (Y2)	Technology Skills	Y21	0.910	VALID
	Trust in Technology	Y22	0.895	VALID
	Technology Performance Measurement	Y23	0,854	VALID
Marketing Orientation (Y3)	Market Orientation	Y31	0,886	VALID
	Marketing Innovation	Y32	0,875	VALID
	Market Segmentation	Y33	0,885	VALID
Innovative Training (Z1)	Participation in Training	Z11	0.948	VALID
	Training Methods	Z12	0.957	VALID
	Training Content	Z13	0.923	VALID

Source: Results of data processing with PLS

Figure 2: Outer Model Path Diagram

4.1.2 Construct Validity

The Construct Validity test aims to ensure that the constructs measured in the study have sufficient validity. This is done by examining the extent to which the indicators used to measure the construct consistently and accurately reflect the essence of the construct. In other words, the Construct Validity test evaluates whether the indicators measure the intended construct and whether the construct can represent Data to model the prognosticators of luxury consumption: A partial least squares-structural equation modeling approach (PLS-SEM).

Table 2: Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

Variable	Dimension	AVE	Information
Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential (X1)	-	0.814	
	Platform Accessibility	0.855	VALID
	Business Continuity	0.830	VALID
Business Performance (Y1)	Operational Efficiency	0.864	VALID
	-	0.860	
	Market Share	0.860	VALID
Technology Adoption (Y2)	Product or Service Quality	0.860	VALID
	Sales Growth	0.860	VALID
	-	0.792	VALID
Marketing Orientation (Y3)	Technology Skills	0.792	VALID
	Trust in Technology	0.792	VALID
	Technology Performance Measurement	0.792	VALID
Innovative Training (Z1)	-	0.781	VALID
	Market Orientation	0.781	VALID
	Marketing Innovation	0.781	VALID
	Market Segmentation	0.781	VALID
	-	0.744	VALID
	Participation in Training	0.779	VALID
	Training Methods	0.769	VALID
	Training Content	0.838	VALID

Source: Results of data processing with PLS

4.1.3 Discriminant Validity

The Discriminant Validity test ensures that each construct in the study can be clearly distinguished. This is done by comparing each construct's Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value with the square value of the inter-construct correlation. If the AVE value is greater than the square of the inter-construct correlation, then it can be concluded that the constructs have sufficient discriminatory validity. The Discriminant Validity test helps ensure that each construct can be clearly distinguished without overlap or confusion between constructs (Liengard, 2024).

Table 3: Nilai Cross Loading

	Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential (X1)	Business Performance (Y1)	Technology Adoption (Y2)	Marketing Orientation (Y3)	Innovative Training (Z1)
X1.1	0.919	0.874	0.892	0.855	0.887
X1.2	0.892	0.801	0.894	0.782	0.860
X1.3	0.911	0.849	0.891	0.788	0.859
X1.4	0.887	0.849	0.860	0.796	0.822
X2.1	0.894	0.867	0.895	0.823	0.868
X2.2	0.911	0.848	0.857	0.810	0.836
X2.3	0.881	0.829	0.849	0.824	0.852
X2.4	0.893	0.839	0.854	0.826	0.852
X3.1	0.936	0.862	0.893	0.823	0.862

X3.2	0.901	0.866	0.835	0.764	0.803
X3.3	0.884	0.871	0.816	0.795	0.851
X3.4	0.919	0.850	0.868	0.806	0.848
Y1.1	0.869	0.935	0.842	0.843	0.838
Y1.2	0.853	0.925	0.856	0.848	0.870
Y1.3	0.883	0.905	0.901	0.828	0.892
Y1.4	0.890	0.945	0.856	0.844	0.868
Y2.1	0.861	0.869	0.910	0.881	0.888
Y2.2	0.859	0.875	0.895	0.853	0.873
Y2.3	0.815	0.737	0.854	0.724	0.837
Y2.4	0.883	0.832	0.899	0.805	0.855
Y3.1	0.766	0.740	0.806	0.886	0.801
Y3.2	0.739	0.807	0.796	0.875	0.837
Y3.3	0.811	0.825	0.807	0.885	0.856
Y3.4	0.848	0.830	0.836	0.890	0.821
Z1.1	0.527	0.854	0.902	0.830	0.900
Z1.2	0.570	0.841	0.798	0.787	0.853
Z1.3	0.797	0.747	0.817	0.810	0.837
Z1.4	0.764	0.831	0.887	0.818	0.844
Z2.1	0.623	0.772	0.828	0.824	0.885
Z2.2	0.663	0.769	0.809	0.806	0.870
Z2.3	0.749	0.822	0.829	0.777	0.826
Z2.4	0.763	0.816	0.877	0.771	0.848
Z3.1	0.694	0.816	0.815	0.830	0.884
Z3.2	0.637	0.874	0.892	0.855	0.667

Source: Results of data processing with PLS

The table shows that the cross-loading value of each indicator shows a more significant contribution to the corresponding construct compared to other constructs. Therefore, in the context of this study, it can be concluded that the discriminant validity of the variables tested is quite valid.

4.1.4 Composite Reliability

Reliability Composite Reliability tests are used to assess the internal reliability of constructs measured in research. This method checks how consistent the indicators used are in measuring a construct. A high Composite Reliability value indicates that the indicators consistently measure the same construct.

This is important because it shows that these indicators can be relied upon to measure the construct in question, making the measurement results more consistent and reliable [55]. Thus, Composite Reliability tests help ensure the validity and consistency of the constructs measured in the study.

Table 4: Composite Reliability Dan Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Dimension	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential (X1)	-	0.979	0.981	Reliable
	Platform Accessibility	0.943	0.959	Reliable
	Business Continuity	0.932	0.951	Reliable
Business Performance (Y1)	Operational Efficiency	0.947	0.962	Reliable
	-	0.907	0.961	Reliable
	Market Share	0.907	0.961	Reliable
	Product or Service Quality	0.907	0.961	Reliable
Technology Adoption (Y2)	Sales Growth	0.907	0.961	Reliable
	-	0.946	0.938	Reliable
	Technology Skills	0.946	0.938	Reliable
Marketing Orientation (Y3)	Trust in Technology	0.946	0.938	Reliable
	Technology Performance Measurement	0.946	0.938	Reliable
	-	0.912	0.935	Reliable
Innovative Training (Z1)	Market Orientation	0.912	0.935	Reliable
	Marketing Innovation	0.912	0.935	Reliable
	Market Segmentation	0.788	0.935	Reliable
	-	0.962	0.967	Reliable
	Participation in Training	0.905	0.934	Reliable
	Training Methods	0.899	0.930	Reliable
	Training Content	0.807	0.912	Reliable

Source: Results of data processing with PLS

The PLS analysis showed that all constructs in this study had Cronbach alpha values >0.6 and composite >0.7. This indicates that these constructs can be considered reliable. Thus, it can be concluded that this research model shows good consistency and that the instruments used have been tested reliably.

4.2 Evaluate the Inner Model

After the outer model evaluation is complete, the analysis continues on the inner model. Evaluation of the inner model involves assessing the coefficient of determination (R-squared), predictive relevance (Q-squared), goodness of fit, and inner weight. The coefficient of determination measures how well the model can account for variations in the dependent variable. Predictive relevance (Q-squared) measures the model's ability to predict the value of an unobserved dependent variable. The goodness of fit is used to evaluate how well the model fits the observed data, while inner weight measures the strength of inter-variable relationships in the model [59].

Figure 3: Inner Model Path Diagram

4.2.1 Coefficient of Determination

The coefficient of determination, or R-squared, is a measure to evaluate how well a regression model can account for variations in the dependent variable. The Coefficient of Determination ranges from 0 to 1, where the higher the value, the better the model can explain variations in the data. In the context of data analysis, the Coefficient of Determination is used to assess how much variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variable in the model. In other words, the coefficient of determination helps determine the adequacy of the model in explaining the observed phenomena.

Table 5: R-Square

	R Square
Innovative Training	
• Participation in Training	0.948
• Training Methods	0.957
• Training Content	0.923
Average	0.943
Business Performance	0.908
Technology Adoption	0.961
Marketing Orientation	0.881
Average	0.917

Source: Results of data processing with PLS

Based on the *R-Square value*, shown in the picture of the SMART PLS analysis results above, after multiplying by 100%, the value of the coefficient of determination of the Innovative Training variable is 94.3%, which means that it gets a direct influence from the independent variable directly while variables outside the study explain the rest. In addition, for business performance variables, technology adoption and marketing orientation influenced this study by 91.7%, while other constructs outside this study influenced the rest.

4.2.2 Predictive Relevance

Predictive Relevance is a measure used to evaluate a model's ability to predict the value of an unobserved dependent variable. Typically, this measure is evaluated using cross-validation methods or by dividing the data into two parts: training data and test data. The higher the Predictive Relevance value, the better the model can predict new data or data not involved in the model creation process. In other words, predictive relevance helps assess the quality and reliability of the model and make predictions beyond the data used in model creation.

Q-Square through the following formula:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - R^2_1) \times (1 - R^2_2)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0.943) \times (1 - 0.917)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (0.057) \times (0.083)$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - 0.0047$$

$$Q^2 = 0.995$$

Based on the q-square calculation above, it can be stated that the predictive relevance model reaches 0.995 or 99.5%; this shows that the analysis has the appropriate predictive relevance.

4.2.3 Goodness of Fit

The goodness of Fit evaluates how well a statistical model matches the observed data. This measure reflects the extent to which the model can explain variations in the data. The higher the Goodness of Fit value, the better the model fits the data and describes variations. In the context of data analysis, Goodness of Fit assists researchers in determining how well the model fits the observed empirical data and how well the model can explain the patterns and relationships present in the data.

The value of goodness of fit can be known in the following calculation:

$$\text{The goodness of fit} = \sqrt{AVE \times R^2}$$

$$\text{Goodness of fit} = \sqrt{0.811 \times 0.934}$$

$$\text{Goodness of fit} = 0.870$$

These results show that the combined calculation in the structural measurement model has a value above 0.870, which shows that empirical data follows the model.

4.3 Hypothesis Testing

The next stage in hypothesis testing is to estimate the path coefficients assessed based on T-statistic values. The estimation shows the relationship of latent variables in the bootstrapping procedure. The measured item shows significance if the T-Statistic value exceeds 1.96 and the p-value is less than 0.05 at a significance level of 0.05 (5%). The parameter coefficient indicates the direction of positive and negative influence on the initial sample and how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent. Here is a path coefficient that gives an idea of the value of T-Statistic.Path Coefficients.

Table 5: Path Coefficients

	Original Sample	T Statistics	P Values
X1 -> Y1, Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential -> Business Performance	0.545	4.309	0.000
X1 -> Y2, Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential -> Technology Adoption	0.415	4.202	0.000
X1 -> Y3, Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential -> Marketing Orientation	0.545	5.526	0.000
Z1 -> Y1, Innovative Training -> Business Performance	0.422	3.386	0.001
Z1 -> Y2, Innovative Training -> Technology Adoption	0.579	5.831	0.000
Z1 -> Y3, Innovative Training -> Marketing Orientation	0.844	4.596	0.000
X1 -> Z1 -> Y1, Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential -> Innovative Training -> Business Performance	0.397	3.345	0.001
X1 -> Z1 -> Y2, Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential -> Innovative Training -> Technology Adoption	0.545	5.901	0.000
X1 -> Z1 -> Y3, Export Cloud Market Platform Based on Local Potential -> Innovative Training -> Marketing Orientation	0.795	4.628	0.000

Source: Results of data processing with PLS

5. METHODOLOGISTS

First is the influence of the local potential-based *export cloud market* platform; in the table, it can be seen that business performance has a positive and significant influence on the quality of the local potential-based *export cloud market* platform with a parameter coefficient value of 0.545. This can be seen from the T-statistics of $4.309 > 1.96$ and p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. From these statistical calculations, it can be concluded that the local potential-based *export cloud market* platform influences improving business performance in this research sample, so H1 states that the local potential-based *export cloud market* platform has a significant effect on business performance, so the hypothesis is accepted. This is important given the increasing trend of technology use in business operations, and these findings confirm that export cloud market platforms based on local potential can be an effective tool for MSMEs to improve business performance. This

research is supported by findings from previous studies highlighting the importance of technology adoption in improving MSME business performance. Research by [60] found that using information technology, including cloud platforms, can increase MSMEs' productivity and operational efficiency. Similar findings were also revealed by a study by [61] which emphasized that technology adoption can help MSMEs reduce costs, improve service quality, and expand MSME market reach. In addition, research by [49] also highlights the importance of digital platforms in increasing the competitiveness of MSMEs in the global market. MSMEs find that digital platforms can help MSMEs to expand market reach, increase product accessibility, and accelerate business processes [50].

Second, in the table, the influence of the local potential-based export cloud market platform shows that technology adoption positively and significantly influences the quality of the local potential-based *export cloud market* platform with a parameter coefficient value of 0.415. This can be seen from the T-statistics of $4.202 > 1.96$ and p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. From these statistical calculations, it can be concluded that the local potential-based *export cloud market* platform influences improving business performance in this research sample, so H2 states that the local potential-based export cloud market platform significantly affects technology adoption, so the hypothesis is accepted. Several previous studies have supported research results that show a positive relationship between technology adoption and the quality of digital platforms, especially in the context of MSMEs. Research from [58] found that MSMEs that adopt information and communication technology (ICT) tend to have more quality and efficient e-commerce platforms. MSMEs highlight the importance of technology integration in business processes to improve competitiveness and operational effectiveness [62]. In addition, research by [43] also supports our findings by showing that technology adoption in the context of online business significantly impacts service quality and customer experience.

Third, the influence of the *export cloud market* platform is based on local potential. The table shows that marketing orientation positively and significantly influences the quality of the local potential-based *export cloud market* platform with a parameter coefficient value of 0.545. This can be seen from the T-statistics of $5.526 > 1.96$ and p-values of $0.000 < 0.05$. From these statistical calculations, it can be concluded that the local potential-based *export cloud market* platform influences increasing marketing orientation in this research sample, so H3 states that the local potential-based *export cloud market* platform has a significant effect on marketing orientation, so the hypothesis is accepted. Research supports the finding that marketing orientation has a positive influence on the quality of digital platforms has been widely done. The research that supports this finding is a study conducted by [61]. In its research, MSMEs found that a strong marketing orientation significantly influences the development of market-responsive digital platforms. Another study that supports these results is research conducted by [42] on e-commerce platforms. MSMEs are finding that a strong marketing orientation can increase the effectiveness of e-commerce platforms in attracting customers and improving the online shopping experience. These results are consistent with findings showing that marketing orientation positively affects the quality of export cloud market platforms based on local potential [5].

Fourth, regarding the effect of innovative training, in the table, it can be seen that business performance has a positive and significant influence on the quality of innovative training, with a parameter coefficient value of 0.422. This can be seen from the T-statistics of 3.386 > 1.96 and p-value 0.001 < 0.05. From these statistical calculations, it can be concluded that innovative training improves business performance in this research sample. H4 states that innovative training significantly affects marketing orientation, so the hypothesis is accepted. This adds a new dimension to our understanding of business development strategies in the digital age, where the ability to adopt innovations and new technologies is key to maintaining competitiveness. Several studies have corroborated the findings that innovative training positively impacts MSME business performance. One of them is research by [19], which found that innovative training can improve the operational efficiency, productivity, and innovation ability of MSMEs in the construction sector. This study's results align with the study's findings, showing that innovative training contributes positively to MSME business performance in the context of the export cloud market platform [63].

Fifth, regarding the effect of innovative training, in the table, it can be seen that the adoption of technology has a positive and significant influence on the quality of innovative training, with a parameter coefficient value of 0.579. This can be seen from the T-statistics of 5.831 > 1.96 and p-value 0.000 < 0.05. From these statistical calculations, it can be concluded that innovative training influences increasing technology adoption in this research sample, so H4 states that innovative training has a significant effect on marketing orientation, so the hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that MSMEs with access to quality innovative training tend to be better prepared to face technological demands in the MSME business, which can increase the competitiveness and growth of MSMEs. Another study that supports the results of this study is a study conducted by [64]. Research finds that innovative training has a significant positive impact on technology adoption by MSMEs in the manufacturing industry sector in Taiwan. Research finds that innovative training organized by local governments helps businesses improve their understanding of technology and facilitates the implementation of new technologies in production processes [49]. Another study that supports the findings is research by [65], showing the influence of innovative training on technology adoption by MSMEs in Malaysia. Innovative training has a positive and significant impact on MSMEs' technology adoption.

Sixth, regarding the effect of innovative training, in the table, it can be seen that marketing orientation has a positive and significant influence on the quality of innovative training, with a parameter coefficient value of 0.844. This can be seen from the T-statistics of 4.596 > 1.96 and the p-value of 0.000 < 0.05. From these statistical calculations, it can be concluded that innovative training improves marketing orientation in this research sample, so H6 states that innovative training has a significant effect on marketing orientation, so the hypothesis is accepted. This aligns with previous findings from the literature showing that innovative training can enhance MSMEs' marketing capabilities, enabling them to better compete in an increasingly complex and changing market. This research is consistent with several previous studies that highlight the important role of innovative

training in improving the marketing orientation of MSMEs. Research from [66] found that marketing-focused training can improve marketing capabilities and business sales strategies in Australia. This finding aligns with research results showing that innovative training positively and significantly impacts business marketing orientation [52]. In addition, research by Khan et al. (2020) also supports the findings by showing that innovative training can improve the marketing capabilities and sales strategies of MSMEs in Asia [67].

Seventh, the export cloud market platform is based on the local potential for business performance, technology adoption, and marketing orientation; in the table, it is explained that innovative training can provide positive and significant mediation on the relationship between the local potential-based export cloud market platform with business performance, technology adoption, marketing orientation. This can be seen by acquiring parameter coefficient values that reach 0.397, 0.545, and 0.795. In addition, significant influences can be seen from T-statistic values of 3.345, 5.901, and 4.628 > 1.96 and p-values of 0.001, 0.000, and 0.000 < 0.05. Based on this, statistically, it can be concluded that innovative training can significantly mediate the relationship between the local potential-based export cloud market platform with business performance, technology adoption, and marketing orientation in this research sample so that H7 states that the local potential-based export cloud market platform has a significant effect on business performance, technology adoption, and orientation, with mediation innovative training received. Several previous studies support the findings that innovative training mediates between the local potential-based export cloud market platform and business performance, technology adoption, and MSME marketing orientation. One of the relevant studies is research by [68], which examines the effect of innovative training on digital adoption and service quality on business sustainability, thus emphasizing the need for strategic alliances of port terminals in Indonesia. Innovative training positively and significantly influences MSME business performance through technology adoption [54]. In addition, research [69] supports the finding that adaptive training for the analysis of chemistry teaching practices generates innovative components in initial teaching training in schools. Comprehensive business training can provide a foundation for pharmacists to create financially viable practice models [70]. In addition, research [71] also training on manufacturing processes and supply chains improves decision-making, problem-solving, and interpersonal communication skills.

The outer model includes an assessment of the indicators or variables used in constructing the model. The first step in this evaluation is to check convergent validity. Convergent validity is used to ensure that each indicator has a significant contribution to measuring the construct in question. This is indicated by the high and significant level of loading factor in each indicator. Next, construct validity is examined, including evaluating AVE (Average Variance Extracted) and loading factors. The AVE must exceed a value of 0.5 to indicate that the construct has sufficient variance to be considered valid [55]. In addition, discriminant validity is also checked to ensure that each construct is distinguishable. This is done by comparing the AVE value with the squared correlations between the constructs. In addition, construct reliability is also checked using Cronbach's

alpha and Composite Reliability (CR) values [56]. The outer model evaluation also includes reliability comparisons between indicators to ensure consistency between indicators used in the construct.

6. CONCLUSION

This study answers the problem statement raised about the influence of export cloud market platforms based on local potential on business performance, technology adoption, and marketing orientation of MSMEs by considering the role of innovative training as a moderation variable. The main finding of this study is that innovative training has a significant role as a mediator in the relationship between the local potential-based export cloud market platform and business performance, technology adoption, and MSME marketing orientation. The implication of these findings on theory and practice in business management is that investing in innovative training can help MSMEs optimize technology platforms to improve business performance, adopt new technologies, and develop effective marketing strategies. However, the study had limitations, including limitations in geographic and sample coverage, as well as limitations in the coverage of control variables. For future research, expanding the geographical and sample coverage and considering other factors that can influence the relationship between the local potential-based export cloud market platform and the variables studied is recommended. Thus, future research can provide a more holistic understanding of the dynamics affecting MSMEs in the digital age.

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